

TECHNICAL SUMMARY

Payment for Ecosystems Services – Focus on Landscapes and Forests

By Rishi Basak. Working Paper, 2017

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INTRODUCTION

Many of the world's ecosystems are not managed sustainably. Payment for ecosystem services schemes incentivize farmers to adopt more sustainable land management practices. This study outlines the concept in more detail, showcases examples of successful program implementation from around the world and highlights opportunities for commercial lenders to become more involved – generating sound financial returns while protecting the environment and improving life in the local communities where projects take place.

WHAT ARE PAYMENTS FOR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Payment for ecosystem services involves compensating farmers for adopting sustainable management practices on their land.

In practice, these schemes involve a series of payments (seasonal, annual or other agreed frequency) to land/natural resource managers in return for environmental services over-and-above what the ecosystem would have provided without sustainable management practices.

Payments are made by beneficiaries of the services provided: private individuals, local communities, businesses, government agencies, impact investors etc.

In the case of agriculture, ecosystem services provided by improved land management include:

- Soil conservation
- Water quality
- Pollination
- Biodiversity conservation
- And carbon sequestration.

The figure below outlines additional services in typical agricultural systems:

Source: (Forest Trends et al. 2008)

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment estimates over 60% of the world's ecosystems are not managed sustainably (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). In order for farmers and land managers to adopt sustainable practices, contracts are put in place between consumers and suppliers of ecosystem services; an approach funded by government programs and/or private sector investment.

The World Bank references the following associated benefits:

- It can be a source of new financing
- It can be self-sustaining- creating incentives for providers and consumers
- It can lead to efficiency gains - promoting the provision of services whose benefits outweigh cost

Payment schemes can be output-based – payment is made based on specific environmental outcomes (e.g. carbon sequestered, or water pollution).

Or input-based - payment is made based on adoption of a specific practice or technology thought to lead to an increase in ecosystem services (e.g. zero-tillage).

WHO IS SUCCESSFULLY IMPLEMENTING CSA

Payment schemes for ecosystem services have been successfully implemented all over the world.

In France, Perrier Vittel pays landowners over \$200 per hectare per year to adopt improved agricultural practices and to reforest sensitive water filtration zones so the bottler can benefit from improved water quality.

In Panama, deforestation near the eponymous canal was causing significant erosion and siltation problems, putting freshwater supplies at risk – meaning dredging, at a cost of \$60 million per year, was required. Forestry insurance company ForestRe established a watershed protection program, paying farmers to plant trees and change farming practices.

Additionally, the company created a bond that canal users can purchase, compensating farmers who adopt sustainable practices.

Bond owners, who include international companies like Sony and Walmart, benefit from reduced shipping insurance premiums.

The Althelia Climate Fund, based in Luxemburg and London, finances payment for ecosystem services schemes in several countries, including: Kenya, Peru, Guatemala and Brazil. The projects they fund reduce greenhouse gas emissions by improving agricultural and forestry practices.

In Costa Rica, the government, an NGO and private hydroelectric utilities partnered with local landowners to improve watershed services through better forest management. Landowners receive payment (a combination of funds from government and utilities) to protect and manage woodland (between \$45 and \$70 per hectare per year). Landowners who reforest obtain larger sums (\$116 per hectare per year).

In Vietnam, payments for forest environmental services have generated about USD 85 million in revenue, with most payments coming from hydroelectric utilities.

Similarly, **the Equitable Payment for Watershed Services project in Tanzania** has been in place since 2006. The enterprise is a partnership involving two international NGOs (CARE International and the World Wildlife Fund), a British policy research institute (the International Institute for Environment and Development), Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, a water utility and Coca Cola. The program focuses on reducing sediment loads in two river

basins providing water to Dar es Salaam and Tanga, compensating upwards of 450 participating upstream farmers adopting practices that reduce soil erosion.

In Kenya, farmers are paid to help create and maintain wildlife corridors. Participating farmers in the Wildlife Lease Conservation Programme receive about \$4 per hectare to leave land unobstructed and adopt other sustainable practices - livestock grazing for example. For most landowners, this means revenue between \$400 and \$800 per year. Payments are made at the beginning of the school term, providing the cash flow needed for families to educate their children. The program started in 2000 with just two landowners. Now there are 350 participants protecting 55,000 acres, with many more waiting to join.

The Costa Rican Payments for Environmental Services Program provides payments to landowners who adopt sustainable forest management practices. This government-run program helps protect primary forest, and promote secondary forest productivity, as well as forest plantations for commercial production.

Payments to landowners vary based on the ecological goods and services produced, from \$64 per hectare per year for the conservation of vegetative cover to \$107 for reforesting degraded or abandoned agricultural lands. The scheme has more than doubled forest cover in the country since its inception in 1997.

The program is financed by revenues from a fossil fuel sales tax, and agreements have recently been signed with private bottling companies, municipal water utilities, irrigation water users and other water

users, such as hotels, further covering program costs.

The World Bank has been supporting payments for ecosystems services schemes since the early 2000's.

Examples include:

- The Ecomarkets Project in Costa Rica (US\$32.6 million loan)
- And the Regional Integrated Silvopastoral Ecosystem Management Project in Colombia, Costa Rica, and Nicaragua (US\$ 4.5 million grant via the Global Environmental Facility).

Silvopastoral systems improve pasture productivity through nutrient recycling. They increase production of fruit, fuelwood, fodder and timber. And shade from trees can benefit livestock production (especially dairy herds) and help diversify production, in addition to sequestering more carbon and increasing biodiversity.

Land users enter into contracts with the program, which requires adoption of practices that will increase greenhouse gas sequestration and biodiversity in exchange for annual payments over a period of two to four years. Contracts also stipulate prohibited practices, such as burning in pastures and cutting primary or secondary forest.

The program provides technical assistance to smallholder farmers and pays “incentives for Eco-Services” ranging between US\$74 and US\$6,000 in Colombia, depending on location, ecosystem services provided and size of the land under management.

Payments are based on an index of environmental

service provision, with farmers paid based on the improvement in their score over time.

More recently, the World Bank provided a US\$10 million loan to the Government of Albania for a similar program to promote sustainable land management in rural upland areas prone to erosion.

Regional development banks have also gained experience with payment for ecosystem services schemes. **The Asian Development Bank** has supported this approach through capacity development, policy advice and pilot projects. They also found that private sector players are increasingly willing to participate in such schemes in this region.

Key lessons learned by ADB:

- The importance of improving the quantification of ecosystem services
- The coordination of reinforcing policies
- And developing more efficient governance structures.

The African Development Bank (AfDB) has also shown keen interest in the concept. In 2015, it released a report and voiced interest in building an agenda for the implementation of schemes in Africa. The AfDB has promoted the use of payments for ecosystem services to complement projects such as the Forest Investment Program and the Congo Basin Forest Fund.

And a few private banks are starting to get involved. Since 2007, Brazil's Bradesco has been working with the Government and the Amazonas Sustainable Foundation to implement the Forest Stewardship Program.

The program provides payments to indigenous communities and other land users to prevent deforestation.

Water in Ecuador's capital is supplied by watersheds in and around protected areas in the Condor Bioreserve. FONAG is a program that supports forest restoration and vegetation cover to help improve water quality. A municipal water utility and The Nature Conservancy have partnered with Fondo Enlace, a socially-responsible private bank, to implement the program - established thanks to seed funding from The Nature Conservancy and the Water and Sewage Metropolitan Enterprise of Quito.

This seed money is held in a private trust controlled by a board of Directors, comprising funders and key stakeholders in the area's water supply, including: a hydro power company, a brewery and a beverage manufacturer, who all benefit from cleaner water. The institutions represented on the board provide an annual contribution to the trust fund.

FONAG uses interest from the trust fund, as well as donations, to finance projects. 2% of revenue generated by the water utility from paying customers goes to the fund - providing a long-term mechanism that uses revenues from equity to finance activities that improve the ecosystem's ability to produce water of sufficient to supply Quito Metropolitan District and the surrounding area.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMMERCIAL BANKS AND OTHER FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

Payment for ecosystem services schemes enable farmers and other land users to learn new, more

productive management practices, helping generate revenue from the sale of their products. They also receive payments for the ecosystem services they provide - through carbon credit sales for example.

Lenders and investors who finance such schemes receive interest on the amount loaned, or cash dividends from the profit created by productivity gains and/or sale of environmental commodities.

In addition to generating good financial returns and improving the environment, projects often foster gender equity and help improve the livelihoods of the local communities where projects take place: raising living standards, providing better access to environmental and social services, and enhancing food security and resilience to environmental changes.

CASE STUDY - ALTHELIA CLIMATE FUND

The Althelia Climate Fund, based in Luxemburg and London, finances reduced carbon emissions from improved agriculture and forestry practices. It has raised over US\$200 million to manage projects for the payment of ecosystem goods and services.

As a specialized investment fund, it attracts capital from private and public institutions, such as the European Investment Bank, the Netherlands Development Finance Company, the Church of Sweden and Finnfund, by offering reduced loss exposure on their investment; achieved via a guarantee from a donor agency, in this case USAID, who guarantee 50% of the capital raised by private investors.

Examples of projects financed include: financing cacao production in Peru and sustainable charcoal in Kenya. In Peru, Althelia has made a US\$12 million investment (with debt swap fund Fondo de las Americas), over a seven year period, to help conserve 570,000 hectares in a biodiversity-rich area.

Part of the investment is towards a farmers' cooperative of over 1000 members. The cooperative works with its smallholder members to improve agricultural practices and produce certified "zero-deforestation" organic and fair-trade cocoa.

Farmers and forest users who adopt sustainable practices generate revenues from the sale of certified cocoa and timber, in addition to payments received for carbon emission reductions (through carbon credit sales) and other ecosystem services (e.g biodiversity and water conservation). 85% of profit generated goes to the farmers, with the balance used to pay for technical assistance and for delivering cash dividends to investors.

Similarly, the Kenyan project - US\$10 million over eight years - will help preserve 200,000 hectares of forest and grasslands by paying smallholder farmers and forest users to manage the land so more carbon can be stored. In addition to generating sound financial returns and improving the environment, projects further gender equity and improve livelihoods of local communities.

Projects financed by Althelia use rigorous carbon accounting standards so emission reductions can be recognized in key carbon markets and programs.

Sources: Althelia Ecosphere (2013); European Investment Bank (2016); McNeil and Rayment (2015)